

USING THE CONFUSED LOGICAL CHAIN METHOD IN ASSESSING STUDENT KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract: It is not necessary to prove that education is the main criterion of human development all over the world. One component of knowledge is evaluation of acquired knowledge. The use of modern methods in the implementation of evaluation in the educational process is therefore an important task. The proposed method for fair determination of students' knowledge level and increasing their activity in classes using the method of interactive confused logical chain. By using the method for the science of theoretical mechanics, it is shown that it is possible to quickly, fairly and transparently assess the level of students' knowledge.

Key words: theoretical mechanics, statics, kinematics, dynamics, force, equation, meeting forces, static exact problem, motion, speed, acceleration, circular motion, law of dynamics, differential equation, connection.

Great changes are being made in the field of education as well as in all areas of our country. The number of existing educational courses in higher educational institutions is increasing with modern courses, and the number of students is constantly expanding and increasing. For example, 5 state and non-state higher educational institutions have been added to the existing 3 higher educational institutions in Namangan region in recent years. Therefore, the increase in the number of students is the need of the hour to provide them with quality education and to use fair, quick and transparent methods of evaluating the level of knowledge. In the future, the issue of using the widely used confused logical chain method in the classes of the taught subjects is urgent.

Pedagogical scientists have carried out many studies on effective teaching of students with the help of pedagogical technologies and will continue to do so. Organizing an activity using a Venn diagram in the course of the lesson [1,4,10,12,19,25] given in works. About the organization of the learning process using the interactive cluster method [3] practical solutions are given in the work. About ways to increase student activity during organized training [2,6,11,14,15,16,17,18] important studies have been carried out in the works.

Research on the assessment of the level of knowledge of students of higher educational institutions using the method of confused logical chain [7,8,20,21,22,27] are detailed in the works. Issues of electricity production using wind energy [5,23,24] seen in cases.

Pedagogical experiments prove that the "confused logic chain" method is one of the most effective methods for determining the level of students' knowledge of theoretical mechanics. This method is distinguished by its ease of use in the course of mid-term assessment and final assessment in order to determine whether students have mastered the subject within a subject of science. When using this method, the student is able to combine concepts related to the studied topic such as formulas, phrases, definitions, theorems related to the science of theoretical mechanics with information on several studied topics, and to match the correct ones from among them. should be able to. In this case, the set of facts related to the topic is presented to the attention of students in a case where the chronological order of cause and effect is confused (broken). Students should be able to correctly place the task in order.

We use the method in the process of teaching the topic "Plane parallel motion" of the kinematics department of theoretical mechanics. Information about quantities and formulas on the subject is provided by the method of confused logical chain. The teacher distributes a copy of the table corresponding to the number of students in the audience to the students of the group. After studying the given table in detail, students write down the answer number for each question listed on the left and the corresponding number on the right. Then the teacher collects the answers from all the students, checks them and announces the results. Below is a table corresponding to the above topic.

Determine compatibility:

1	State the law of plane parallel motion?	1	12 1/c
2	Show the formula for finding the speed of an arbitrary point of a body in parallel motion?	2	$\left. \begin{aligned} x_A &= f_1(t) \\ y_A &= f_2(t) \\ \varphi &= f_3(t) \end{aligned} \right\}$
3	If the speed of the center of the wheel with a radius of 0.5 m is 6 m/s, what is its angular speed?	3	$\vec{v}_B = \vec{v}_A + \vec{v}_{AB}$

4	Tell the definition of instantaneous center of velocities?	4	Crankshaft mechanism, wheel movements
5	Give examples of plane parallel motion?	5	A point on a flat shape where the velocity is zero at a given time

Correct answers (3,1,2,5,4).

Now we will try to use the method of confused logical chain for a branch of the science of theoretical mechanics - the branch of kinematics. The results of this score can be used to test students' knowledge in a non-traditional way to quickly determine the level of mastery of the studied unit by the student and to obtain intermediate evaluation scores. In this case, the number of questions will be more compared to the evaluation of one subject. Because the higher the number of questions, the higher the level of objectivity. At the beginning of the academic year, professors of the department create a bank of questions, which are regularly filled and improved. The table covering all topics of the theoretical mechanics kinematics department is given below:

Determine compatibility:

1	The movement is in the plane $x = 10 \cos 2t$, $y = 10 \sin 2t$ What figure is the trajectory of a point given by the law?	1	$x = f_1(t)$, $y = f_2(t)$, $z = f_3(t)$
2	What is a trajectory?	2	The movement of the movable number system in relation to the fixed number system
3	What can you say about the magnitude and direction of the point's velocity?	3	5 m/c
4	State the theorem about progressive motion?	4	$\vec{a}_B = \vec{a}_A + \vec{a}_{AB}$
5	Show the formula for the components of the acceleration of an arbitrary point of a body in circular motion?	5	$\vec{a}_{kor} = 2\vec{\omega}_e \times \vec{v}_r$
6	Show the formula for finding the acceleration of an arbitrary point of a body in plane parallel	6	In the forward movement of a rigid body, all its points draw a uniform trajectory, have velocities

	motion?		and accelerations equal in amount and direction.
7	What is the definition of a derivative action?	7	The trace left by a point in space during its movement
8	Write the formula for Coriolis acceleration?	8	$\vec{a} = \vec{\varepsilon} \times \vec{r} + \vec{\omega} \times \vec{\omega} \times \vec{r} = \vec{a}^{ay} + \vec{a}^{mi}$
9	The point is in the plane $x=3t$, $y=2t^2-5$ acts according to the law. Find the velocity of the point at $t=1$ second?	9	The point is equal to the first-order product of the radius vector over time, and it is directed in the direction of movement along the attempted trajectory.
10	Show the law of coordinate method of giving point movement?	10	$x^2+y^2=10^2$ circle

Correct answers (10,7,9,6,8,4,2,5,3,1).

By using this method to determine the level of knowledge acquired by students in the course of a lesson in theoretical mechanics, it becomes possible to quickly, transparently and fairly assess the level of knowledge of students. For this, the teacher prepares question bank materials covering all departments of the subject. It is natural that the number of questions offered to students increases with the increase in the weight of the material. However, after a certain number of questions (25-30) using the method of confused logical chain causes a number of inconveniences. Therefore, it is necessary to use this method without increasing the number of questions to 25 when conducting the final assessment.

Determine compatibility:

1	How do you know how to add a system of forces?	1	Bog'lanish jismning faqat koordinatalarini cheklaydi va vaqtga bog'liq emas
2	Show the conditions of analytical equilibrium of a system of forces in a plane?	2	$\sum F_{kx} = 0, \sum F_{ky} = 0, \sum m_A(\vec{F}_k) = 0$
3	Show the unit of measurement of torque?	3	$y = (5/4)x^2$ parabo'la
4	What kind of problem is called an indefinite	4	Tekis shaklning berilgan onda tezligi nolga teng bo'lgan nuqtasi

	problem?		
5	Show the conditions of analytical equilibrium of a system of forces located freely in a plane?	5	$\sum F_{kx} = 0 , \sum F_{ky} = 0$
6	Write the law of circular motion with uniform acceleration?	6	$x = e^{-bt} (c_1 \cos \sqrt{k^2 - b^2} t + c_2 \sin \sqrt{k^2 - b^2} t)$
7	Law of point motion $x=2t, y=5t^2$ given by law. What is the shape of the trajectory?	7	nm
8	Tell the theorem about the projection of the velocities of two points of a flat figure?	8	A body isolated from an external environment will continue to remain at rest or move in a straight line unless acted upon by a force.
9	What is the instantaneous center of velocity?	9	If the number of unknown reaction forces in the problem is equal to or less than the number of equilibrium equations
10	Write the formula of the theorem of addition of accelerations in the complex motion of a point?	10	$A(F_{ish}) = -f \cdot N \cdot s$
11	The first law of dynamics	11	The projection of the velocities of any two points of a body moving in a parallel plane onto a straight line connecting these points is equal to
12	Write the law of damping oscillatory motion?	12	$\varphi = \varphi_0 + \omega_0 t \pm \frac{\varepsilon t^2}{2}$
13	What kind of connection is a geometric, stationary connection?	13	Geometric (triangle, parallelogram, power polygon) and analytical (through projections)

14	Show the differential equation of motion of a rigid body?	14	$m\ddot{x}_c = \sum R_x^e, \quad m\ddot{y}_c = \sum R_y^e,$ $m\ddot{z}_c = \sum R_z^e$
15	Show the formula for calculating the work done by the force of friction?	15	$\vec{a}_{abs} = \vec{a}_{korich} + \vec{a}_{nis} + \vec{a}_{kor}$

Correct answers (13,5,7,9,2,12,3,11,4,15,8,6,1,14,10).

Based on the above, it is possible to come to the following conclusion: as a result of using the method of a confused logical chain, students can organize the subjects they have studied in science, divide them into components, compare them with other parts of the subject, and obtain information about the newly studied subject. skills such as understanding are formed. Regular use of this method in lectures gives students the opportunity to systematically study scientific materials, organize, divide and differentiate what they have learned. As a result, the level of knowledge of students increases significantly. Alternative opportunities for the teacher to objectively determine the level of students' knowledge in a quick way, to successfully conduct intermediate and final evaluations will be expanded.

When planning to evaluate students' knowledge using the method of confused logical chain, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- it is necessary to expand the bank of questions related to science by topic.
- it is necessary to create a bank of logical, easy-to-solve examples and problems related to the topics.
- in order to determine the level of mastery of the subject of science, it is necessary to compile the options of tables consisting of 5-10 questions at least equal to the number of students in the group.
- the professor-teacher offers the option of tables consisting of 10-20 questions to students for mid-term assessment.
 - it is recommended to prepare tables of 15-25 questions for the final control assessment.
 - Samples of the question bank and example-problem bank and the order of execution should be regularly published on the website of the department.

In short, the method of the confused logical chain is one of the modern and convenient methods for determining the level of students' knowledge. This method is distinguished from other assessment methods by the fact that it is

especially effective in checking students' knowledge on one topic of science, on one chapter of science, and during midterm control..

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